

Bio-security measures at poultry farms and its overview

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Biosecurity is securing protection from micro-biological organisms it includes all the cumulative measures that can or should be taken to keep disease away from a farm and to prevent the transmission of disease (by humans, insects, rodents, and wild birds/animals) from an infected farm to neighboring farms

Cleaning and Disinfection of poultry shed

- Cleaning and disinfection play a vital role in the management of poultry, helping to avoid various bacterial, viral, fungal and protozoal diseases. After vacating the shed of all birds, preferably in one operation or in the shortest possible time, the house should be disinfected and kept vacant hereafter for sufficient time until arrival of new flock.
- Remove all drinker, feeders, curtains, bamboo basket brooders (hovers). Clean and wash them thoroughly with water jets and then washing soda solution. Afterwards dip them in a virucidal disinfectant as per the manufacturer's instructions for time and dilution rate. Then sun dry for a day.
- Remove all organic material e.g., manure, litter, feathers, dust, etc., preferably after spraying 5% to 10% formalin and collecting the above in closed containers e.g. gunny bags or plastic bags. All organic matter mentioned above should be disposed away from farm premises
- Clean all fans, bulbs/tubes, wire nets and water tanks. (For automatic drinking system, remove all water from pipeline. Fill the whole watering system with 5% to 10% sodium hypochlorite, keep it overnight or at least 3 to 4 hours. Flush the system with plain water to remove the solution.
- Bamboo basket brooders from all IBD affected sheds should be disposed by burning and new brooders should be used for new batch.

Chemical Treatment: Floors should be soaked with strong solution of caustic soda flakes (NaOH) with pH above 12 for 12 hours to 24 hours. Then drain out water completely.

Dose: Caustic soda flakes (NaOH)* 11 to 12 gms per litre of water. 100 litres of such solution should be used for 1000 sq. feet. Washing Soda (Na₂CO₃) 50 to 60 gms/litre of water or 5 to 6 kg/1000 sq.feet. Rewash the flooring by spraying any of the below mentioned disinfectants

1. Quaternary Ammonium compound or chlorine 10 to 20 ppm to be used either in the form of bleaching powder or sodium hypochlorite (containing 20% available chlorine)
2. Iodine in dilution to provide 1000 ppm

In case of ticks, mite and lice infestation, the shed may be sprayed with Cythion at the rate of 80 ml to 160 ml per 10 liters of water. Here it is very important and mandatory to follow the safety precautions, as spraying of this type of insecticides is hazardous.

Painting: White wash the shed with lime solution with 1% kerosene and 5% formalin.

Fumigation: Fumigation with Formaldehyde gas is a common practice. Mixing 40 ml of formalin with 20 gms of potassium permanganate for a volume of 100 cubic feet. Double strength is sometimes used in specialized needs. Fumigation is more effective in presence of humid atmosphere than dry. Hence, spraying the walls and floors with water before fumigation is necessary. All the cracks, crevices and windows should be sealed while the fumigation is in process (normally 40 hours). Formalin is poured over the potassium permanganate, into the pots beginning from the farthest end of the house. For effective fumigation it is desirable to have wetness (humidity) inside the house and temperature above 24 C.

At the end, use spray of virucidal disinfectants commercially available in the market. Consult local technical expert/veterinary expert for choosing the disinfectants and follow manufacturer's instructions for the usage. After cleaning and disinfection, keep the house vacant for a period of 15 days. It is advisable to undertake spraying of virucidal disinfectant 48 to 72 hours before actual arrival of chicks.

Whitewash: Given below is the formula, which gives proportion of different ingredients to be included in lime.

3.5 litre Cream of lime (prepared by mixing 4.5 kg of quicklime in 9 litre of water)
100 ml Formalin
1 litre Kerosene
5 litre Water

To the whitewash thus prepared, add following ingredients for special effects.

50 gms Alum (to prevent rubbing off of white wash)
100 ml Molasses (for better penetration in wood)
50 gms Bar soap dissolved in 4.5 litre of boiling water (to give it oil paint like gloss)

White washing of house with this mixture will serve the basic purpose.

Biosecurity in poultry farm:

Biosecurity is in order to prevent the introduction and spread of poultry pathogens into the farm and shed. Strict implementation of biosecurity measures is advised. Use of effective disinfection program, sanitation, general maintenance, personal hygiene, adopting effective control strategy to restrict men and material movement, feed vehicle, wild birds and other animals together will help in achieving good biosecurity in and around farm premises and prevent breeder flock from getting exposed to the poultry and perform better. Ssematimba *et al* (2013).

Key points for achieving good biosecurity:

1. The poultry farm site should have isolated location.
2. The ideal poultry-breeding farm should be at least 3 km from any commercial or backyard poultry.
3. Farm boundary should be fenced by chain-link fence buried to a depth of 18 inches and topped with barbed wire to prevent the entry of unauthorized persons and animals.
4. Keep the doors and gates locked at all time.
5. Provide separate vehicle and foot dips at entrance of the farm. Change the vehicle, foot dip and hand sanitizer solution at every point at least twice in a day.
6. Restrict the visitor's entry and maintain record of the same.
7. Provide shower facility, changing of dress and foot ware before entering in the farm or premises.
8. Farm should have toilet and hand wash facilities separate from the poultry house.
9. No pet and other animals are allowed in and around the poultry housing.
10. Provide hand sanitization and foot dips at entrance of each shed.
11. Restrict the movement of men and material within the farm premises.
12. All surrounding area around the house should be level and free from vegetation, debris, unused equipment that could harbour vermin, rodent.
13. Avoid water pooling between the sheds.
14. Visit youngest and clean flock first and oldest and ailing flock at last in the day to prevent cross-transmission of pathogens to young birds.
15. Farm supervisor should be given responsibility of one age group and while visiting different sheds he should follow all the biosecurity measures.
16. If equipment is to be used from other farm or section, it should be cleaned and disinfected properly before it is brought onto/ in the premises/shed.
17. All breeding operations should be meant for single purpose (Brood and grow or laying) operations and whenever possible single age group principle is to be adopted.
18. The water supply to poultry house should be of satisfactory potable status.
19. When a poultry house is depopulated, all manure is removed from the house and effective cleaning and disinfection procedure is to be followed. Rodent and insect control procedures also to be carried out.
20. Adequate down-time (rest period) between flock placement should be given. A minimum period of four weeks for growers and six weeks for laying house is needed.

21. A continuous integrated program should be in place to control rodents.
22. Microbial monitoring of new litter material and shed monitoring is must before placing new flock.
23. A disease-surveillance program must be followed for all materials used or introduced onto the farm site. This involves examination of each load of floor litter material and consignments of feed for bacterial and fungal pathogens.
24. Poultry flocks are to be regularly monitored for salmonella and other poultry pathogens.
25. A closed post-mortem room with adequate natural light should be near to dead bird disposal area.
26. Sick and dead birds are to be removed from poultry houses as soon as possible and disposed by effective and safe burning method. Dead bird should be carried to post-mortem room in closed plastic bags.
27. Serological and environmental monitoring programs for breeder flocks are necessary components of biosecurity. Serological flock profiling to monitor vaccination and disease challenge will depend on the prevalence of infection and range of diseases in the region of operation.
28. Poultry working personnel should be checked for human salmonella status once in a year.
29. The vaccination crew, needs to follow all the biosecurity protocol.
30. Timely measures for control of flies and pests must be adopted using approved chemicals/methods.
31. Frequent collection and sanitation of hatching eggs, is an effective method to reduce and control the effects of faecal and environmental contamination. Lu *et al* (2003).
32. The sanitized eggs should be stored in clean egg flat.
33. The egg containing flats should be transported to the hatchery in clean vehicle, which should be fumigated or sanitized with a liquid disinfectant. The cleaning and disinfection of vehicles must be a regular part of the hatchery routine.
34. Store the hatching eggs in a clean, dust free cold room used exclusively for this purpose.
35. Monthly monitoring of the cold room should be done by lab.
36. Full records relating to mortality, disease diagnosis, treatment, vaccination, medication, production etc are maintained on an individual flock basis within the farm.

Biosecurity: -

All In All, out: The system is strongly recommended for maximum extraction of genetic potential of birds. It is suggested to have separate brooding and growing facility away from laying facility.

Restriction on Men & Material: Sales persons, egg buyers, servicemen and visitors should not be allowed to enter in. Workers' movement from one age group to other should be minimised to the extent possible. Under no circumstances should men move from laying houses to brooding.

Foot Baths: Foot baths should be provided at the entry of the farm necessarily and each house wherever possible. This foot bath should contain suitable disinfectant in necessary dilution. Water from foot baths should be changed periodically.

Foot Wear: Foot wears (preferably rubber slippers) should be used for changing the foot wear before entering the farm.

Disposal Methods of Dead Birds: The immediate burning or burying of dead birds is an important part of a good disease prevention program.

Incinerators: A good incinerator is probably the best means of disposal, especially in an area where there is poor soil drainage or a danger of contaminating the water supply.

Disposal Pit: A less desirable but acceptable method of dead bird disposal is through the use of an adequately designed and tightly covered disposal pit. A pit of 6 ft (1.83 m) in diameter and 6 ft deep (1.83 m) is large enough to take care of one 10,000 capacity layer unit. It is necessary to remove all dead birds immediately and they should be disposed properly.

Rodent and Pest control: Rodents are major vector and reservoir of Salmonella infection resulting in increase in level of contamination in the environment and transmit the infection to other poultry houses and farm. Therefore, it is necessary to prevent rodent access to feed, water and denying shelter by:

1. Building rodent –proof poultry houses (metal door and concrete floor)
2. Eliminating harborage area inside and outside of house
3. Appropriate house management and sanitation
4. Disposing of dead birds and unused or spilled feed
5. Regular inspection and monitoring of rodent activity
6. Rodent baiting and trapping
7. Control insect vectors (flies and beetles) through good management practices and selection and use of pesticide after cleaning and disinfection. Amass *et al* (2000).

General Disinfectants use and application:

1. Disinfection implies the elimination of all microorganisms in the house, which are pathogenic or have the potential to produce a disease. A disinfectant can be bactericidal at a concentration and bacteriostatic at lower levels.
2. Effective disease control measures by disinfectants will reduce or eliminate the need for medication specially the use of antibiotics. Cost of a sound disinfection program is always much less than the cost of even a short course of antibiotic therapy.
3. Natural disinfectants: The value of sunlight as a natural disinfectant in poultry houses is immense. Desiccation from fresh air and wind will also contribute to the destruction of bacterial load when microbes are exposed. The high temperature will accelerate the destruction of organisms.
4. Chemical disinfectants: Disinfection in farm is carried out by chemical agents. The lethal action of the chemical is expected by their ability to reach with the essential enzymes of the microbes by coagulating or precipitating or denaturing their protein coat.

5. The chemical disinfectants act very effectively when they are easily soluble. Emulsification of phenol in a soap solution enhances the activity of disinfectants.

Reference:

- Amass S. F.; Vyerberg B. D. and Ragland D. (2000). Evaluating the efficacy of boot baths in biosecurity protocols. *J Swine Health Prod.* 8(4):169–173.
<http://poultrybiosecurity.org>
<http://www.cdc.gov/nczved>
- Lu H, Castro A. E.; Pennick K.; Liu J.; Yang Q.; Dunn P.; Weinstock D. and Henzler D. (2003). Survival of avian influenza virus H7N2 in SPF chickens and their environments. *Avian Dis.* 47(3):1015–21.
- Sematimba A. 1.; Hageaars T. J.; Wit J. J.; Ruitkamp F.; Fabri T. H.; Stegeman J. A. and Jong M. C. (2013). Avian influenza transmission risks: analysis of biosecurity measures and contact structure in Dutch poultry farming. *Prev Vet Med.* 1: 109(1–2).

